

NEW PROCUREMENT AND COOPERATION MODELS FOR PLANNING + EXECUTION OF TIMBER BUILDINGS - CASE STUDIES AND VISIONS

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ABSTRACT: Timber construction still suffers from the prejudice of higher costs and complexity. While timber manufacturers set on `lean production` in order to increase productivity, upstream planning phases follow traditional ways (structures) and exclude manufacturers' know how in earlier planning phases. Thus most often manufacturers submit alternative proposals during the tendering that demand a necessary re-design of the architect's planning. Hence previous planning effort is wasted, which is far away from `lean`. One cause has already been pointed out many times: the separation of the design and the execution team. The surprising finding is that design and construction themselves rarely cause complexity. Instead, it is the organization of the process which is lagging behind. In order to achieve process innovation, the *leanWOOD* project provides recommendations on how to work in existing structures and drafts visions for a new understanding of roles and a turnaround in the policy of procurement approaches.

KEYWORDS: *leanWOOD*, timber construction, complexity, case study research, procurement, cooperation, roles;

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

This paper provides first evaluation results of case studies with a special focus on procurement and cooperation models and the evaluation of the alleged complexity of timber buildings. Additionally it provides recognitions on how to improve procurement and cooperation models.

1.2 IDEAL SCENARIO AND REALITY – A LOOK INTO THE MIRROR

In the last two decades the timber manufacturing sector has made unimaginable technological progress by applying lean production methods. Today, timber manufacturers are able to deliver high-quality construction solutions with very short on-site mounting procedures. Parallel to this technological leap, the sprawl of information and communication technologies led to an ideal environment for digital workflow and efficient cooperation between involved actors regarding the planning and execution of industrialized timber construction.

Despite these ideal preconditions, reality shows a distinguished picture.

- › Timber manufacturers and engineers confirm the lack of planning standards that do not respect the needs of industrialized timber construction with a high level of prefabrication.
- › The plannings of architects and engineers need to be completed before production planning or at least when the production starts. Often, late changes regarding the design, technical details, penetrations or through lets, etc. require re-planning and consequently lead to costly re-works on-site (for penetrations, through lets, etc.).

- › The level of detail between timber construction engineering and building service planning is not aligned. Other than in massive construction, especially structural planners and timber construction engineers need firm and binding specifications for installations and ducting in the early phases.

- › So-called `re-design phases` after completion of the tender process put additional stress on the planning team. They are often caused by the necessary alignment of the architect's planning due to changes proposed during the tender process or negotiations with manufacturers. Planners and manufacturers mention different reasons from their point of view:

- Planners complain about the practice of some contractors that dispense exaggerated alternative proposals due to allegedly cheaper constructions solutions, cheaper materials, other suppliers, etc.
- Manufacturers point out that due to missing manufacturing know-how, constructions either neglect timber-appropriate design and planning or optimization potential out of production capabilities, used materials or components had been neglected in the planning phase.

In both cases architects and timber construction engineers are confronted with unspoken accusations of poor planning and unused potential for optimization. Nevertheless, prior to contract awarding, a considerable effort is invested in the tendering planning as a basis for the tender specification. Considering the German or Swiss situation, fee regulations show, that usually at this time the architect has already spent 62% (acc. to the German HOAI³) or 50.5% (acc. to the Swiss SIA 102⁴) of the planning budget. Thus, significant planning effort is wasted by this re-design phase – which does not follow the idea

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³ HOAI 2013. Regulation of Fees for Architects and Engineers.

⁴ SIA 102:2014. Regulation governing architects' services and fees.

of a `lean`-approach. Additionally timber manufacturer are already under the pressure of continuously shortened execution schedules.

Beyond that, timber construction still suffers from the prejudice regarding higher complexity and higher costs than massive construction. These arguments are often produced by clients when decisions on materialization are made. Nevertheless, the technological potential of tackling these obstacles is available – as promoted by the timber construction sector. Therefore the question remains, whether a `leaner` approach in design and planning would enable less complex and more cost-efficient production and execution of timber construction.

1.3 COOPERATION AND PROCUREMENT IN TRANSITION

This unfortunate situation has its roots in the strong traditionally shaped building procedure of massive construction. In projects (especially regarding projects financed by public money) the procurement legislation⁵ separates the planning and the executing actors in order to identify the best bid in a fair competition amongst bidders. With this specification manufacturers and their know-how are excluded from the early design and planning phases. Thus, cooperative and joint developments of architects, planners and manufacturers in order to optimize solutions in the early phases, are not possible.

Figure 1: Traditional procurement and cooperation models separate the design and the execution team and hinder joint development of architects, planners and manufacturers. Source: CCTP

Although the regulations for public procurement only have to be applied for projects above the threshold, a broad range of timber construction projects are affected. Private clients on the other hand would have more freedom and could integrate manufacturers and their know-how in early phases. However, most likely only the traditional way is anchored in their awareness and executing manufacturers are tendered in the later stages of a project.

2 THE WOODWISDOM-NET PROJECT *leanWOOD*

The WoodWisdom-Net project *leanWOOD* was launched in 2014 by research and industry partners from

Germany, Switzerland, Finland and France with the aim to advance planning processes and cooperation models towards the characteristic of timber construction processes. This will be achieved by showing ways to overcome traditional procurement and cooperation models, identifying the actual complexity in the planning and execution of timber buildings and developing guidelines and visions that aim on a turnaround in process and cooperation.

2.1 METHODOLOGY: THE ANALYSIS OF CASE STUDIES

The methodology used in the *leanWOOD* project is based on a case study research approach. In order to visualize the procurement and cooperation model a graph was developed showing the model approach with the relevant actors (roles) and how they are linked together. Actors (roles) such as architects, planners and engineers are shown as dark grey ellipses, executing actors as light grey ellipses. The different lines show how they are linked together.

Figure 2: Symbols for graphical representation of the cooperation models. Source: CCTP

Additionally the complexity of every case study was analysed according to the aspects in the following categories: requirements, design, construction and process. Therefore a set of criteria structured into four categories have been defined:

- > The category requirements contains aspects that are more or less given by the frame conditions of the project and the client. The range of influence is very low. Exemplary aspects are the dimension, the building's standard (Minergy, Passivehouse, etc.) or necessary fire and noise protection standards. The higher the level, the more demanding are the requirements.
- > The category design contains aspects that can be influenced by the architect and early concepts by the engineers. These are geometry, design of openings, system separation, and level of standardisation or prefabrication. The higher the level, the more demanding the planning and execution will get.
- > The category construction contains aspects that can be influenced by the timber construction engineers through their structural planning. These aspects are for example the chosen primary construction system, the design of nodes and stiffening, etc. The higher the level of complexity, the more effort and care has to be brought up in planning and execution.
- > The category process contains aspects that can be influenced by the set-up of the project team and the organization of the cooperation amongst the actors. These are aspects like network planning, early integration of relevant specialist planners or the timber

⁵ The WTO (World trade organization) Agreement on Government Procurement (GPA) rules the contract awarding by means of public money. The WTO/GPA was implemented by the EU by slight adjustments of the EU directives (2004/18/EU and 2004/17/EU).

manufacturer, coordination within the project, data exchange⁶, quality management, etc. These aspects show how design and construction are handled in the process. The lower the levels, the smoother and more efficiently the procedures are able to run. Higher levels indicate barriers within the project organisation or cooperation.

Each category is represented in a spider diagram showing the grades of complexity or level of difficulty from level 1 (low) to 5 (high). See Figure 5, Figure 8 and Figure 11.

For verification, this evaluation has been cross-checked through interviews with all relevant actors of each case study – client, architect, timber construction engineer, manufacturer and site or construction manager.

The evaluation of the case studies was a proof-of-concept. The set of criteria definition will be developed further-on in the *leanWOOD* project - based on experiences from this first assessment

3 CASE STUDIES

3.1 COOPERATION AS DESIGN FACTOR – RESIDENTIAL AND COMMERCIAL BUILDING KALKBREITE (ZURICH)

Figure 3: The inner courtyard of the residential and commercial building Kalkbreite in Zurich. Source: Müller Sigrist Architekten, raumgleiter GmbH.

Introduction

In 2006 the Cooperative Kalkbreite formulated the vision ‘New ways of community-living in the city that contribute to the 2000-Watt-Society’. At that time the plot was used for stabling tracks of the Zurich public transport operators. By using this area as valuable inner-city land-resource, the development was completed in 2014 as a building area around and above the tracks of the tramway incorporating different usages housing, community and working with high-level flexibility.

Today ambitious ecological standards and significantly low individual space consumptions are the built vision of how the 2000-Watt-Society might be realized in future buildings.

Procurement and cooperation model

In order to find a developer, the city of Zurich launched a developer’s competition. The innovative concept of the Cooperative Kalkbreite convinced the jury and they were thus granted the building right (‘Baurecht’) to develop the area. Afterwards, an open architectural competition identified the project with the highest value: it was the concept of the architectural office Müller Sigrist Architekten that followed a traditional block perimeter development with a ‘Rue Intérieure’.

The Cooperative Kalkbreite transferred its vision of cooperation to the planning process as well. All planners and contractors were linked with individual contracts to the cooperative as clients. Currently a lot of associations or other institutional clients use general or total contractor models. They prefer one contact person for their wishes and demands, guaranteed schedules and costs and reduced internal effort. In contrary, the cooperative Kalkbreite wanted to play an active part as responsible decision maker. All planners were commissioned directly – in this way they worked together on an eye-to-eye level and the Cooperative could decide who was commissioned. The only exception was the assignment of the cost and site manager: Due to the large dimension of the project the architectural office assigned an experienced construction management office responsible for cost and site management. For the execution, the tendering and contract awarding of the companies followed the traditional model of single contracts after a mainly public tender process. The contractual relationship and the communication channels are shown in Figure 4: The executing companies were also commissioned directly with single contracts. The cascade model of sub-contractors who can hardly be controlled was thus avoided.

Figure 4: Cooperation model in the residential and commercial building ‘Kalkbreite’ in Zürich acc. to the symbolic described in Figure 2.

The active role of the client was one key factor for the success. Three main actions should be named explicitly:

- > An internal ‘Construction Committee’ (‘Baukommission’) met regularly.
- > A professional expert was designated to moderate decision-making (‘Moderator’) and to ensure that necessary decisions were provided timely to the planning team and the site manager.

⁶ This aspect refers to the implementation BIM in current planning and execution processes. A separate paper from *leanWOOD* is published within the context of the WCTE 2016 ‘Investigating the Interaction of Building Information Modelling and Lean Construction in the Timber Industry’. Author: le Roux, Simon; et al. Thus, hereafter the issue of BIM is not further explained.

- › Two professional client representatives were designated and empowered to steer the planning and construction process from the administrative side – the ‘Project Managers’.

During the entire project the coordinating responsibilities were defined: The two project managers of the cooperative Kalkbreite steered the entire administration from the viewpoint of the purchaser. On the other side the architectural office Müller Sigrist kept the planning and, together with the construction manager, the execution firmly in their hands.

Early decision for timber construction

In order to comply with the vision of the 2000-Watt-Society it is nearly mandatory to implement the ‘Minergie-P-Eco’ standard. This is a voluntary building standard in Switzerland. While the abbreviation ‘P’ refers to the energy-efficiency (comparable to the German passive house standard) the addition ‘Eco’ refers (inter alia) to the embodied energy of the construction. Thus, applying this standard to a building includes CO₂ emissions and resource-efficiency into decision-making for building construction. In the case of Kalkbreite the use of timber was already proposed by the architect in the architectural competition, based on the formulation of the cooperative’s vision of sustainability and ecology. This is a rather scarcely used practice because referring to timber in an architectural completion might cause disadvantages. Generally, cost evaluation in this project stage is based on cost benchmarks from experience. A preconception is that timber construction is about 8 -15% above a standard construction.

However, timber constructions provide a broad range of different options for one construction - which is a plus considering the options it offers. Unfortunately on the other side this makes it difficult to get benchmarks that depict the specific situation. However, in case of the Kalkbreite, the client wanted to assure that the materialisation guarantees the concept with the lowest embodied energy. So, one of the first steps in the preliminary project after the architect was confirmed, was the evaluation of the material concept. At this time it was not possible to construct the entire building in timber.⁷ Thus, the evaluation comprised massive construction versus hybrid construction systems. And with the embodied energy as decision basis, a timber construction for the exterior wall was the appropriate solution. It was designed as a self-supporting timber frame element system clad with plastered insulation panels. The construction and building system (piles and slabs) and the tramway hall on the ground floor were built of reinforced concrete prefabricated elements. In order to base this evaluation of materialisation on a serious foundation, the timber construction engineer was already integrated in the preliminary project – an action which is recommended, but not a commonly used practice.

⁷ Before the new fire regulation BSV 2015 was set into force on 01.01.2015, the application of timber in Switzerland was (acc. to the BSV 2003) limited to six storeys for the load-bearing construction system and eight storeys for façade construction.

The design of the wall by the timber construction engineer

The exterior wall construction system was a prototype in terms of the dimension and the extended plastering on a soft fibreboard. Additionally the timber construction engineer office avoided the usual steel supporting construction on the edge of the concrete slabs and designed it totally in timber.

The additional intention (in order to follow the vision of the Cooperative) was to design a construction that could be offered and executed by a broad range of manufacturers. This was confirmed by the timber manufacturer in the interview – the system was well thought through and the manufacturer offered a tender without an additional ‘optimization proposal’. Further it was possible to implement the planned construction without major changes compared to the previous submission planning.

Evaluation

Figure 5: leanWOOD evaluation of the residential and commercial building Kalkbreite (Zurich) according to methodology described in 2.1.

In Figure 5 the leanWOOD evaluation (as described in 2.1) according to the aspects requirements, design, construction and process shows:

- › High requirements arose from the project context itself. It was the dimension of the project, the situation in the inner city in the middle of a highly frequented traffic node that challenged the building site.
- › The design of the architect and the planning team was able to reduce the complexity by an intelligent design of openings, element dimensions and system separation. The high level of geometry could not be avoided – it was given by the high level of required flexibility in usage. However, the system with load bearing concrete piles and slabs and non-load-

bearing interior design offered a high level of flexibility until the end of the project.

- › Overall the construction system of the exterior wall was an easy-to-implement solution.
- › The process was (compared to other projects) characterized by sound network planning and a good coordination. In general a lot of involved actors had years of experience in timber construction. However, the team or single planners had never been working together in a previous project and the data exchange was on the level of today's common practice.

The evaluation in *leanWOOD* showed that the complexity in the project was not given by timber construction per se or little experience. The complexity arose from the very high requirements given by the site and dimension of the project and the actual standards in planning processes.

Results

The early evaluation of the material concept according to the lowest embodied energy supported the application of timber. The integration of the vision towards a 2000-Watt-Society paves the way to introduce timber construction more and more in urban areas. Additionally the fast and easy-to-install construction met the needs of the challenging building site. The investment costs of about 1,790 €/m² net floor area (for the cost groups 300 and 400 according to the DIN 277) proves the excellence of the team. Actually the project of the Cooperative Kalkbreite is the built vision of cooperation and a frontrunner to induce cooperation into a project team and a building. In April 2016 it was awarded with the 'Hans Sauer Price' for Social Design.

3.2 AN EXEMPLARY EARLY COOPERATION, APARTMENT HOUSES UAL DA FLEX (GRAUBÜNDEN)

Figure 6: Apartment houses 'Ual da Flex' in Savognin (Graubünden). Source: Uffer AG

Introduction

Usually architects and engineers are most likely chosen due to recommendations and references or identified by architectural competitions. Manufacturers on the contrary are – unless it is a public or a private client – chosen by a tendering based on the lowest bid principle. In order to break up this upward circle and to find new ways of acquiring projects, the timber manufacturer Uffer AG has started to engage in project development

as well and hence realizes high-quality and innovative timber buildings focusing on the creation of regional value. Thereby trust and the commitment to deliver sound quality in planning and construction are important principles.

Procurement and cooperation model

Historically, high levels in timber building culture are a common practice in Graubünden. Nowadays the region is known as the cradle of contemporary timber architecture and innovative timber technology. Due to this background, the timber manufacturer started the project development for new apartment houses with a competition between two architects. The affiliation to trust and quality was the reason that subsequently the development company Ual da Flex AG was founded: it is a partnership amongst the successful architectural office, the timber manufacturer and an external investor. The intention behind this cooperation model was to raise the motivation of all actors to contribute to the project success by sharing the profit. The Ual da Flex AG commissioned the timber manufacturer as total contractor for the planning and construction of the apartment houses. In order to avoid redundant ping-pong processes during the planning, the cooperation model in Ual da Flex was based on an early and very close cooperation between architect and timber manufacturer. Before the planning started, the timber manufacturer decided on the relevant built-ups and construction details which had been proven valuable in previous projects. Hence the architect started the planning right from the beginning with a catalogue of basic construction details. In order to use synergies, the production planning of the manufacturer was based on the construction plans of the architect (scale 1:50) and comprised all further detailing for execution. This procedure is not common in the cooperation between architects and timber construction experts. However, it proved to be very successful – there were no significant amendments of the architect's plans.

Figure 7: Cooperation model in the project of the apartment houses Ual da Flex in Graubünden acc. to the symbolic described in Figure 2.

The specialist planners for HVAC and electric installations were commissioned directly – due to good experiences in previous projects. They based their planning on the same drawings. The idea to establish a team with a high level of trust was followed for the denomination of the executing companies as well. Most

of them were commissioned directly. Only building services and electric installations were tendered.

An efficient planning approach

In the interview the architect expressed his satisfaction with the planning approach. In the beginning the wall structure was not defined in detail – only the thickness was fixed by the manufacturer. The first drawings of the architect showed the wall as a `black box` - two lines indicating the thickness. According to him it was not necessary to go into detail. Only when the construction planning was done – lines for the cladding outside and the installation layer inside indicated the multiple layers of the wall structure. Only details relevant for the design were elaborated by the architect.

`A very efficient approach for planning`, resumed the architect. The cooperation model, as it was established in the Ual da Flex project would be his ideal approach especially for larger projects.

Evaluation

Figure 8: leanWOOD evaluation of the multi-apartment houses Ual da Flex in Savognin acc. to the methodology described in 2.1.

Figure 8 shows the leanWOOD evaluation (as described in 2.1) according to the aspects requirements, design, construction and process:

- > High requirements arose from the project context itself: the dimension of the project and the high requirements in noise protection due to owner-occupied⁸ apartments. The Minergie-P standard needed a ventilation system with mandatory heat recovery. Additionally underground parking spaces had to be provided for the new apartments.
- > The complexity of design and construction could be reduced significantly by the efficient cooperation between architect and timber manufacturer.

⁸ In Switzerland a higher standard in noise protection is applied to occupied flats compared to rental flats.

- > This affected the process. The spider-chart depicts the streamlined planning process as well. Only the data exchange followed current standards – it was the exchange of .dwg- and .dxf-files between the planners. Additionally .pdf-files were used to secure information as within the exchange line thicknesses and solids change their appearance.

Results

The project manager of Uffer AG stated in the interview `Timber construction worked out well`. This statement underlines the benefit of the timber manufacturer integrated in the earliest design phase. It led to a very efficient planning without ping-pong and re-design phases. The architectural design underlines the high culture of timber architecture and timber construction in Graubünden. The apartments support highest standards – hence the investment costs are above usual standards for apartment houses. Nevertheless, the evaluation showed the cost-drivers: the necessary underground parking and the elaborate ventilation system.

3.3 PUBLIC AUTHORITIES AS INNOVATION DRIVERS – EUROPEAN SCHOOL (FRANKFURT)

Figure 9: Entrance façade European School Frankfurt
Source: T. Mayer

Introduction

The growth of the big cities in Germany and whole central Europe is ongoing and thus the pressure to provide school and living space is increasing. Fast reactions to changes of the spatial needs are sometimes necessary. In the present case the reorganization and enlargement of the European Central Bank in Frankfurt made a short-term extension of the existing European school inevitable, where most of the children of the employees are taught. 400 pupils from the age of 3 to 8 years should be taught in separated preschool and primary school units. The new building was planned as a temporary building due to building permit reasons and was to be realized in a time frame of 15 months, from starting the first feasibility study to teaching the first lessons in the building. In light of this schedule a school container building was the initial concept of the client. Nevertheless the highly committed architects developed an attractive school building offering excellent spatial qualities by using consequently prefabricated three-dimensional elements. In technical terms the time pressure problem was solved with the implementation of timber space modules. It is also obvious that without an adequate planning process the very short project duration would not have been feasible.

Procurement and cooperation model

Economic efficiency, transparency, competition and equal treatment are the principles of public procurement. Public clients have to act according to the public procurement rules. It seems to be a hardly known fact that there is a significant scope for actions within the existing framework: Functional specifications instead of detailed tender descriptions, the combination of various trades in a single tender description as a logical consequence of prefabrication, the commissioning of planning and building services according to a total contractor model are applicable even today.

The architectural office NKBK developed a feasibility study in December 2013. The positive feedback of the client resulted in a direct order for the architects. The procurement scope corresponds to around 50% of the full working stages 1-8 according to the official scale of fees for services by architects and engineers (HOAI). The execution planning and the construction monitoring were not commissioned. Thus the fee was kept below the threshold for a direct order and a tender procedure for the planning services was not obligatory.

Figure 10: Cooperation model in the project of the European School in Frankfurt according to the symbolic described in Figure 2.

The client, namely the building department of Frankfurt, decided to commit the building services in a functional description procedure. The department had more than 20 years of experience in handling this kind of procedures. The architects developed the building permit planning and, on the base of a template of the client also a functional tender description for the timber works and all trades related to the prefabricated space modules. All areas especially important for the appearance of the building such as the façade and materials were described precisely in very few master details. The construction of the space modules and their connections were left more open and with leeway for the bidders to incorporate their expertise in the offer. The building permit plans, the master details and a structural calculation concept were added to the 80 pages' document of the functional tender description. The tender just asked for two prices, namely the total building services in terms of a general constructor model and the above described planning services the architects were not engaged to deliver. Kaufmann Bausysteme from Vorarlberg clearly were able to win the European wide pure price competition procedure. The company developed the execution planning with the help of the structural engineer merz kley partner from Dornbirn as a

subcontractor. The site supervision was also provided by the executing company. The architects were involved in the execution process only through consulting activities regarding architectural issues. They evaluated the process as very effective and successful from their own economic perspective. The office was not very experienced in timber construction, so the project was a good access to further planning of multi-storey timber buildings.

Evaluation

Figure 11: leanWOOD evaluation of the European School in Frankfurt according to the methodology described in 2.1.

Figure 11 shows the leanWOOD evaluation (as described in 2.1) according to the aspects requirements, design, construction and process.

- > The temporary character of the project allowed to reduce the requirements to minimum standards such as a reduced HVAC-concept (e.g.: natural window ventilation, visible radiators on the sealing)
- > The complexity in design was moderate thanks to a very strict design respecting the rules of modular building principles.
- > Thanks to the strict modular design the construction was feasible without major challenges. Beams of laminated beech timber were used to bridge the large spans of the classrooms.
- > The mayor challenge of the process was the very tight time schedule.

Results

The space modules construction and the cooperative procurement model helped to maintain the very tight time table. The requirement of reusability of the produced modules in potential future buildings was also met. The resulting costs were at around 1'500 €/m² gross floor area BGF (cost groups 300-400 net according to German norm DIN 277) and significantly below the initial cost calculation of the architects. The architectural quality of the project is documented in various, also

international, publications and prizes, for example the timber architecture prize of Hessen (‘Holzbaupreis Hessen’).

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Complexity

The evaluation of the complexity of the case studies in *leanWOOD* shows a very clear picture.

Basically in all case studies the requirements given by the building task and the project context are rather high. Today’s building standards are continuously rising, demanding more sophisticated building constructions. Nevertheless, the fields of design and the construction are the ‘adjustment screws’ of the design and planning team in order to reduce the project’s complexity. Timber construction has a lot of characteristics that provide sufficient and mostly easy solutions for the rising standards: The spider-charts in Figure 5, Figure 8 and Figure *II* show that the levels of complexity in design and construction are rather low. In contrary, these charts show clearly that aspects in the category process have a high level of complexity. Especially in ‘data exchange’ there is a top value in all cases. A further peak can be found in planning and quality management. The case study Kalkbreite is – compared to common practice – an exception. The set-up from the client’s side and the architectural office provided a professional design, planning and execution environment.

Thus the evaluation in *leanWOOD* provides a more differentiated picture of the prejudices. It is not the timber construction itself that causes complexity. Frame conditions and actual process organization often make it impossible to meet the needs of today’s timber construction. The approaches in network planning, data exchange, planning management and the understanding of roles are quite challenging concerning the planning and execution of industrialized timber construction.

4.2 Procurement and cooperation models

The evaluation of procurement and cooperation models in the case studies shows a picture that is quite common in construction today. The Kalkbreite in Zürich was carried out according to the commonly used procedure in the D-A-CH area: An architectural competition as a basis for high architectural quality with subsequent tender processes for the executing contractors. While the architect is mainly chosen by the design approach, the executing companies are selected according to the price criteria.

Further it is also a rather common practice to decide materialisation only after the architectural competition.

With regards to the project Kalkbreite, this was the only disadvantage mentioned by the architect - that timber construction was not explicitly given as a pre-condition already in the architectural competition.

The example of the European School shows that a shift of the main project responsibility from the architect to the timber manufacturer after the building permit phase can be a promising approach. Obviously the quality of the building greatly depends on the planning skills of the timber manufacturer and his willingness to understand and respect the architectural aspects. This model can

be implemented in projects of limited complexity and is also feasible in a public procurement framework.

The project Ual da Flex shows a second cooperation model gaining increasing momentum. Timber manufacturers start to enter the field of project development and offer services as ‘timber construction total contractor’. The manufacturers established their internal planning departments – a pre-condition for the necessary production planning. Thus, design competencies can easily be integrated in these teams and manufacturers are able to offer full services including the planning. Thereby the manufacturers meet the request of clients to have one partner for planning and construction issues. This development moves from the Northern and Anglo-Saxon countries to Middle European countries. The discussion on how this might influence the values of our building culture is increasing especially in the D-A-CH area.

Besides the total contractor models that are more or less offered by larger timber manufacturers, the general contractor models are wide-spread. The effort of individual tendering and subsequent coordination of larger projects is rather high. Smaller architectural offices are sometimes overburdened. Thus the cooperation with experienced general contractors can be advantageous for architectural offices that focus more on the design part in planning and are discharged with the coordination effort on site. Nevertheless, it was often mentioned in the *leanWOOD* interviews that it strongly depends on the attitude of the general contractor. The range of different general contractor policies in terms of cooperative team approach, quality and transparency is differing vastly. On the question of the ideal features of a general contractor, the architects and engineers stated that the cooperation on an eye-to-eye level and flexibility without continuous cost threats are important factors.

4.3 Role models

Timber construction engineer

The timber construction engineer is a specialist planner nearly exclusively spread in Switzerland. Basically the timber construction engineer is a structural engineer with a special education in timber construction. He supports the architect in timber construction design and establishes the link to the manufacturer. In the development Kalkbreite, the engineer was already integrated in the preliminary project in order to evaluate the different materialization concepts.

On one side, the engineer might be seen as one of the many necessary specialist planners in a building project. A closer look reveals the special role: Timber construction planning strongly depends on a broad variety of inputs from other planners. Without detailed specifications on dimensions and characteristics from board and insulation materials, claddings or integrated components, the timber construction engineer is not able to work. His planning is strongly interconnected with others, thus the engineer is demanded to system thinking – more than other specialist planners.

Thus the timber construction engineer, as practiced in Switzerland, would be a suitable solution for other countries. However, in the discussion with Swiss timber construction engineers, this vision appears in a different

light. The engineer's overview on system solutions, technical details in combination with the knowledge in timber structural engineering and static calculations is indispensable. Nevertheless, the integration of the manufacturer would extend the range of the optimization of execution procedures, sufficient material selection and logistics.

Architect

The analysis of the different case studies within the *leanWOOD* project shows the comprehensive understanding of the role of an architect. In the D-A-CH area the architect plays an important role. From history he is seen as the custodian of the building culture. Architectural competitions are quite common (Kalkbreite, Ual da Flex). In contrary, the situation in the Northern European and Anglo-Saxon countries is dominated by total contractor approaches. In this context architects have more supporting roles and have to subordinate the architectural design in most cases to a strict price policy. Most likely, timber manufacturers would appreciate this role of the architect as it might bring streamlined processes without ping-pong planning and a design that meets the needs of timber construction. Concerning coordination there is another discourse of understanding the architect's role in today's timber construction. Historically the architect is seen as the one person managing the building project. Most often national standards list the related tasks such as 'coordination of the services of all participants' and 'management of the team of planners'. However, the superficial descriptions in the standards are too unprecise regarding the characteristics of timber construction. Yet, the coordination effort in building projects is increasing excessively regarding the growing need of necessary specialist planners even in small building projects. Additionally the conquest of BIM⁹ requires new coordination tasks. This opens up a new field for architects that can be compared with the conductor of an orchestra. It is the role of a manager steering a team and coordinating the (net)work of specialists.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS AND VISIONS

The evaluation dialogue in *leanWOOD* between research and practice showed that the most obvious problems in timber construction do not arise from technical aspects. Thus, the necessary fields of actions to establish a planning culture that meets the needs of timber construction are changes in the tradition of procurement and cooperation and a new understanding of roles and cooperation models. In this way *leanWOOD* provides recommendations on how to work in the existing structures as well as visions for necessary changes in (legal) frame conditions. A new approach in procurement and cooperation needs time until the (legal) frame conditions can be shaped and established. Nevertheless, the change towards a new system approach has to start with the definition of the responsibilities and duties of role models in the planning and execution team and re-thinking how teams are set-up and organized.

5.1 SOLUTIONS TO WORK IN EXISTING FRAME CONDITIONS

Thus, more specific descriptions of role models, the related responsibilities and range of the duties of involved actors are needed. Current standards provide the skeleton – it is up to the timber construction sector to refine the role description of architects and timber construction engineers in order to meet the needs of timber construction planning and execution. Especially the task of coordination in timber construction projects has to be discussed. The organization of planning management is lagging as well: Different planning sequences between massive construction and the timber construction have to be adjusted and clarified. A sound and transparent plan delivery management with defined milestones is essential to guarantee planning progress and cooperative refinement of the level-of-detail. These are basic preconditions to apply BIM. And on a long-term view it will be indispensable to integrate these descriptions into national standards.

5.2 RE-THINKING THE TEAM SET-UP

A second field of action is to overcome the tradition of how teams of planners and executing contractors are organized. The first small steps to break up this tradition have already been set. Architects and planners have been selected primarily according to their design approach (most often) in an architectural competition. This selection continues to spread – more and more clients place high value on the planning management and office organization and the atmosphere of trust. Thus pre-qualification procedures are up-coming and show the path towards a selection based on references, quality, skills and trust instead of sole fee reduction.

This policy has already been rudimentarily applied in the selection of executing contractors. Additional selection criteria have been integrated in tender processes for identifying the most eligible executing companies. However, these criteria have most often been solely based on references or apprenticeships. Nevertheless, the price has remained a dominating criterion. The development in the planning sector could be used as a model for the selection of executing contractors. Cities like Copenhagen already practice such quality related selection processes. And public procurement legislation in most countries offers this path already. However, it would be up to clients to set initiatives.

5.3 New procurement and cooperation models

The crucial point to integrate manufacturer's know-how in earlier project stages has different obstacles. From a general point of view the competition system with a focus on the lowest-price principle shaped an environment for competitors on the market. Fair pricing for clients and the motivation to raise productivity for contractors are one side of the medal. Additionally the WTO GPA¹⁰ offers a market without trade-barriers between the countries. The idea behind these regulations is a fair, open and transparent competition for the

⁹ See footnote 6

¹⁰ See also footnote 5

bidders. Thus, the procedure needs an independent tender and is based on the exclusion of companies in the early planning phases – a way to guarantee equal treatment of all bidders. On the other side this framework supports a price spiral downwards, hinders cooperative development before tender and excludes know-how for optimization.

Figure 12: Bringing the knowledge of the executing manufacturer into the early design phase in order to enable joint development of architects, engineers and timber manufacturers on eye-level. Source: CCTP

Cooperative approaches based on the idea of joint development have already been tried in the past. These were, for example, the `Working group model` in Switzerland, several `Bauteam` models in Germany (derived from the `Bouwteam` in the Netherlands). However, these models could not make a real breakthrough.

In the `Working group` model the relevant contractor was involved in the early design and planning phases. In order to comply with procurement, he had to disclose his know-how in the tender. However, contractors achieved no real benefit from providing their know-how.

In the `Bauteam` model teams of architects, planners and executing companies offered their services together. Design, planning and costs estimation were developed within the team based on a functional description. The client could choose the best solution out from the proposals submitted by different teams. Experiences showed that it was necessary that one takes the role of coordination. Most often it was a company experienced as a general contractor. In this way the model had a very high congruence with total contractor models or – in case of a contract design with separate commissioning of planning and executing team – with a general contractor model.

The `Bauteam` approach offers a model with contracting parties cooperating on eye-to-eye level (without the thumbscrew of costs by the general contractor). In future a timber manufacturer could take the role of the executing coordinator while the architect would be responsible for coordinating the planning team.

A modified total contractor approach is also gaining increased momentum. There have already been public procurement calls, for example in Switzerland, addressing a full service competition of specialist planners from architecture, timber construction and building services in cooperation with timber construction manufacturers. Yet, this practice is not wide-spread, but it is gaining attractiveness especially for entities and cities committed to the 2000-W-Society vision, where

timber construction contributes to reaching ambitious targets concerning embodied energy.

5.4 Visions

As visions for the future following developments can be drafted:

- > A change in the traditional procurement avoiding the exclusion of relevant actors. Competition is necessary, but it has to be done earlier in the project in order to allow network planning. Cost capping or cost frames might allow dynamic development in network planning approaches with a high degree of cost certainty for the client.
- > Materialization is issued earlier. This would be the basis for a design, appropriate to the chosen construction material. As a consequence preliminary studies to evaluate different implementation options would become more important.
- > The selection criteria for contractors shift from price to quality and skills orientation. This would mean more and precise specifications in the tender respectively procurement process.
- > Goals and objectives are defined in the beginning. This would be the task of the client. Current strategies to check the situation on the market (with alternative positions in the tender specifications) and to decide later on the precise building or implementation standards have to be reflected in the remuneration of the planning team.

The work in the *leanWOOD* project will be continued until May 2017. This paper provides a small insight into the development of future procurement and cooperation models and represents the current stage of work in the project. The authors are open to feedback and comments in order to improve the results in the interest of the entire process chain. It should be noted that topics such as liability or other frame conditions such as economic structures, BIM, etc. could not be discussed in the context of this paper. However, they are addressed in the *leanWOOD* project.

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